
Literature Review On The Application Of A Novel Cellular Automata Classifier for COVID-19 Prediction and Visualization

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August 18, 2020

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	A brief history of The Coronaviridae Family	2
3	Cellular Automata Preliminaries	3
3.1	Cellular Automata: definitions	3
3.2	Cellular Automata transition rules . . .	4
4	The Application Of A Novel Cellular Automata Classifier for COVID-19 Prediction	4
5	Summary	14
6	Author Biography	15

Figure 1

The Coronaviridae family is included in the Nidovirales order together with the Arteriviridae and Roniviridae. The first-ever recorded coronavirus related disease was feline infectious peritonitis back in 1912. However, until the late 1960s, the coronaviruses were not recognized as pathogens responsible for human diseases (common cold), and it was in 2003 when human coronaviruses (HCoVs) received worldwide attention with the emergence of the severe and acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), produced by a coronavirus (SARS-CoV), that has infected more than 8,000 people in 32 countries, killing about 10%.

The increase in research on coronaviruses soon led to the discovery of another human coronavirus (HCoV-NL63), which is prevalent in 7% of hospital patients and has been associated with bronchiolitis and, possibly, conjunctivitis. [8] Fast-forward to the present day coronavirus now represents one of the worst pandemics in the past decades even though The virus that causes COVID-19 is not the most deadly nor the most contagious. According to Dr. Luis Enjuanes Coronaviruses have been identified in mice, rats, chickens, turkeys, pigs, dogs, cats, rabbits, horses, cows, and humans. Coronaviruses are associated mainly with respiratory, enteric, hepatic, and central nervous system diseases. In humans and fowl, coronaviruses primarily cause upper respiratory tract infections, while

porcine and bovine coronaviruses establish enteric infections that result in severe economic losses and crisis. [8] With the explosion of recorded information and machine learning, biochemists and virologists for the first time found it necessary to familiarize themselves with databases, artificial intelligence and the algorithms needed to extract the correlations of records, and in turn, have put these to good use in the exploration of phylogenetic relationships, and in the applied tasks of hunting genes and their often valuable products. Machine learning in this coronavirus crisis has generated a new impetus in datasets to be analyzed and applied to project the cases of the pandemic.[4] .

1 Introduction

Numerous outbreak prediction models for COVID-19 are being used around the world each day to make important decisions and enforce confinement control measures. We can see for COVID-19 global pandemic prediction, that epidemiological and virologists are relying on statistical models to base their judgment and redirect their research. Due to a high level of uncertainty and lack of essential data, standard models have shown low accuracy for long-term prediction. The current volume is an effort to bridge just that range of exploration, from nucleotide to an abstract concept, in contemporary AI research. That bridge must also join computer scientists with laboratory biochemists on how imputed knowledge will be used. A variety of target problems, and perhaps a hand-crafted representation for each, is embraced in the roster.[3] There

is an obvious detriment to premature standardization, but it is daunting to see the difficulties of merging the hardwon insights, the cumulative world knowledge, that comes from each of these efforts to contain this pandemic, this literature review is simply an emphasis on one of the most important models that used cellular automata for predicting the cases of this pandemic which went unnoticed by many experts.[4]

2 A brief history of The Coronaviridae Family

According to a set of professors at The Institute of Virology, the University of Würzburg in Würzburg, Germany the Coronaviruses were recognized as a group of enveloped, RNA viruses back in 1968 and were accepted by the International Committee on the Taxonomy of Viruses as a separate family, the Coronaviridae, in 1975. By 1978, it had become evident that the coronavirus genomic RNA was infectious, and by 1983, at least the framework of the coronavirus replication strategy had been perceived. Subsequently, with the application of recombinant DNA techniques, there have been remarkable advances in the understanding

Figure 2: Diagram of the structure of a coronavirus virion

of the molecular biology of coronaviruses by virologists, which led to the existence of a mass structural data concerning coronavirus genomes, mRNAs, and proteins. Nevertheless, there are still large gaps in the scientist's knowledge, in areas such as the genesis of coronavirus subgenomic mRNAs or the function of the coronavirus RNA-dependent RNA polymerase.[26]

It is safe to say that the diseases caused by coronaviruses have been known for much longer than the agents themselves. Possibly the first coronavirus-related disease to be recorded was feline infectious peritonitis, as early as 1912. The diseases associated with infectious bronchitis virus, transmissible gastroenteritis virus, and murine hepatitis virus were all well known before 1950. However, in the late 1960s, it was then that academic virologists realized that a coronavirus was responsible for human disease, the common cold. The advances of the last few years, for example, in the molecular analysis of coronavirus protein immunogenicity or the identification of coronavirus receptors, have undoubtedly given an impetus to studies on coronavirus pathogenesis. [26]

The emergence of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) in Guangdong Province, China, in 2002, and its subsequent spread in Asia and Canada clearly exemplified the vulnerability of societies and economies to a novel, highly pathogenic respiratory agent (Stadler et al. 2003; Peiris et al. 2003b). The outbreak, which was halted solely by the quarantine of exposed individuals and the use of conventional prevention measures such as surgical masks was paralleled by an international, collaborative scientific effort to develop means for therapeutic and preventive intervention.

Fast-forwarding to present day The coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) that originated in Wuhan, Hubei area, China, is considered one of the worst pandemics that the human race faced in the last 100 years. [22]

Figure 3: Example of a Viral cycle of MERS coronavirus. MERS, Middle East respiratory syndrome.

3 Cellular Automata Preliminaries

Stephen Wolfram in his book "A New Kind of Science" [29] states that despite their very simple construction general cellular automata have not been considered until the 1950s. Yet in the 1950s - inspired in various ways by the advent of electronic computers - their where several different kinds of systems equivalent to cellular automata were independently introduced. A variety of precursors can be identified. Operations on sequences of digits had been used since antiquity in doing arithmetic. He also adds that Finite difference approximations to differential equations began to emerge in the early 1900s and were fairly well known by the 1930s. And the invention of Turing machines in 1936 was most importantly based on thinking about arbitrary operations on sequences of discrete elements.

The best-known way cellular automata were introduced according to Stephen Wolfram was through the work of John von Neumann in trying to develop an abstract model of self-reproduction in biology - a topic that had emerged from investigations in cybernetics. Around 1947 von Neumann began thinking about models based on 3D factories described by partial differential equations. Soon he changed to thinking about robotics and imagined perhaps implementing an example using a toy construction set. By analogy to electronic circuit layouts, he realized however that 2D should be enough. And following a 1951 suggestion from Stanislaw Ulam, he simplified his model and ended up with a 2D cellular automaton. The particular cellular automaton he constructed in 1952-3 had 29 possible colors for each cell, and complicated rules specifically set up to emulate the operations of components of an electronic computer and various mechanical devices. To give a mathematical proof of the possibil-

Von Neumann neighborhood
 $\{(0, 0), (\pm 1, 0), (0, \pm 1)\}$

Moore neighborhood
 $\{-1, 0, 1\} \times \{-1, 0, 1\}$

Figure 4: two-dimensional neighborhoods example

ity of self-reproduction, von Neumann then outlined the construction of a 200,000 cell configuration which would reproduce itself. Von Neumann appears to have believed that something like this level of complexity would inevitably be necessary for a system to exhibit sophisticated capabilities such as self-reproduction [15] [12].

3.1 Cellular Automata: definitions

A Cellular Automaton (CA) is basically an finite/infinite lattice of finite state machines, called cells. The cells of a d-dimensional CA are positioned at the integer lattice points of the d-dimensional Euclidean space, and they are addressed by the elements of \mathbb{Z}^d .

Formally, A CA is a 4-uple $B = (S, N, d, f)$ where S is a finite set of possible states, N is the cellular neighbourhood, $d \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ is the dimension of A , f is the local cellular interaction rule, also referred to as the transition function.

The cells change their states synchronously at discrete time steps. The next state of each cell depends on the current states of the neighboring cells according to an update rule. All cells use the same rule, and the rule is applied to all cells at the same time. [17]

The neighboring cells may be the nearest cells surrounding each cell, but more general neighborhoods can be specified by giving the relative offsets of the neighbors. [12] Let

$$N = (\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2, \vec{x}_3, \dots, \vec{x}_n)$$

be a vector of n distinct elements of \mathbb{Z}^d . Typical two-dimensional neighborhoods are represented in the Figure below.

The smallest non-trivial one-dimensional neighborhood is the size two neighborhood (0, 1). This is the neighborhood of the xor-CA. This case is one-way as information can not flow to the right. [17]

If the configurations are shifted by half a cell at each step we obtain the radius - $\frac{1}{2}$ neighborhood. The space-time diagram is then symmetric:

If the configurations are shifted by half a cell at each step we obtain the radius - $\frac{1}{2}$ neighborhood. The space-time diagram is then symmetric:

3.2 Cellular Automata transition rules

The Elementary cellular automata is one of the simplest one dimensional CA where each cell has two possible states (0 or 1), and rules that depend only on the nearest neighbors (left, right). As a result, the evolution of an elementary cellular automaton can be described by a table specifying the state a given cell will have in the next generation based on the value of its neighbors on the left and the right and the value of the cell itself. Since there are 8 possible binary states for the three cells neighboring a given cell, there are a total of $2^8 = 256$ elementary cellular automata, each of which can be indexed with an 8-bit binary number [12] (Wolfram 1983, 2002). For example, the table giving the evolution of rule 30 (30=00011110) [28] is illustrated as follows:

The evolution of a one-dimensional cellular automaton can be illustrated by starting with the initial state

(generation zero) in the first row, the first generation on the second row, and so on. For example, the figure below illustrates the first 20 generations of the rule 30 elementary cellular automaton starting with a single black cell:

The complete set of 256 (rules 0-255) elementary cellular automata can be found in Wolfram's book here are some samples illustrated below for a starting condition consisting of a single black cell.

4 The Application Of A Novel Cellular Automata Classifier for COVID-19 Prediction

Previous research conducted by Pokkuluri Kiran Sree and Usha Devi Nedunuri showed a successful development of a novel classifier HNLCA, which can process real-time datasets to predict the number of deaths and cases in the near future as well as the number of people that can recover, the rate at which this virus spreads, transmission within the boundary, and of the boundary. The developed classifier is adaptable to various dynamics inputs and can process data of different lengths. Even though it is a preliminary work to predict trends of COVID, they have developed the first novel classifiers with dynamic rules with cellular automata. [22]

A large number of existing studies in the broader literature have concluded that cellular automata are a versatile classifier that can process dynamic data and

that the general rules of CA can be represented by the equation : $T(n+1)=T(n-1)+T(n)+T(n+1)$ The transition from one state to another state is defined by the rules. Wolfram has defined the rule number to be a decimal equivalent of the next state as shown in Tables 1 and 2. In this context, when Pokkuluri Kiran Sree and Usha Devi Nedunuri consider three neighborhoods and two states for cellular automata, they give subconsciously 256 different next states. and they also set the equation for the complemented Rule 51 as follows : $q_i(t+1) = q_i(t)$ and for the Non complemented 238 rule : $q_i(t+1) = q_i(t)+q_{i+1}(t)$ [22]

TABLE 1. Rules with neighborhood

Neighbors	111	110	101	100	011	010	001	000	Rule
R-51	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	51
R-238	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	238

TABLE 2. Rules without complementation

1.	250	q_{i-1}, q_{i+1}
2.	204	q_i
3.	240	q_{i-1}
4.	170	q_{i+1}
5.	0	0

the authors have considered various parameters for predicting the spread of the virus listed below.

1. Vu: Vulnerable people in the region number
2. InOu: Inward and outward movement of the people
3. Ti: Transmission rate of possible infections
4. Te: Transmission rate of possible exposure
5. . Vo: Volatility of transfer per person today
6. P: Total population in the regions
7. D: The probability of death
8. R: The probability to recover
9. E: The probability to get effected

The authors have driven the further development of the design of hybrid non-linear cellular automata (HNLCA) .

They used the following Algorithm (HNLCA Algorithm) : Input: Nine parameters collected and DNA

Figure 5: COVID-19 predictions with different parameters. (Vu: Vulnerable people in the region number, InOu: Inward and outward movement of the people, Ti: Transmission rate of possible infections, Te: Transmission rate of possible exposure, Vo: Volatility of transfer per person wrt today, P: Total population in the regions, D: The probability to death, R: The probability to recover, E: The probability to get affected).

sequence Output: Prediction(rate of death, infected, and curable)

1. step 1: Embedding the sequence and preprocess the parameters.
2. step 2: Use the rules as Stated 1,2, and 3.
3. step 3: Feature identification.
4. step 4: Construct the H

the researchers of the paper observed that the error rate is much less in HNLCA, which is 11.8 % better compared to SRV. HNLCA reports an accuracy of 78.8, which is way better than long short-term memory.

the application of the algorithm of the authors provide a more accurate prediction of COVID-19 cases and deaths as shown in the chart :

Performance of HNLCA and comparisons conducted in the paper is represented in Figure 6.

Some authors have driven the further development of using Machine Learning to assess Covid-19 risks, they developed a COVID risk stratifier model that classifies people into different risk cohorts, based on their symptoms and validate the same. Clustering analysis is used on the unlabelled dataset to learn different cohorts and patterns in the data. [23]The most popular

Figure 6: Performance of HNLCA and comparisons (HNLCA: Hybrid non-linear cellular automata, LSTM: Long short-term memory, AdaBoost: Adaptable boosting, SVM: Support vector machine, REG: Regression, SVR: Support vector regression).

clustering algorithm used in healthcare applications is the K-means clustering algorithm. This is used when there is numerical and continuous clinical data. [16] K-means algorithm groups similar data points together and identifies the underlying patterns within them. It uses distance-based metrics to group data into K different clusters by calculating K different centroid and assigning every data point to the nearest centroid. The K-Modes algorithm can be explained by these mathematical equations [16] :

$$d_1(X,Y) = \sum_{j=1}^m \delta(X_j, Y_j)$$

where (X_j, Y_j) is defined as

$$(X_j, Y_j) = \begin{cases} 0 & (X_j = Y_j) \\ 1 & (X_j \neq Y_j) \end{cases} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$C(Q) = \sum_{i=1}^n (Z_i, Q_i) \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

where Z is the categorical variables ranging from A0, A1...An and Zi is the i element and Qi is near the cluster center. [23]

they based their recherche on the K-MODES ALGORITHM :

Input: Data of dimension N*X, N being the number of observations, and X being the number of features. K: No of clusters.

1. Step 1: Randomly select K different modes from the input data such that $C_{i,j} = 1, 2, \dots, K$.
2. Step 2: Compare each data point in the cluster to each data point from the input data set.
3. Step 3: Add 1 for every dissimilarity encountered and 0 for equal values as shown in equation (1)
4. Step 4: Assign each individual to the closest centroid. (2)

5. Step 5: Calculate mode for each feature for every centroid.
6. Step 6: Repeat steps 2 to 5 until no changes are obtained in the data assignment to the centroids

The authors employed a silhouette which is basically a measure of similarity between a data point and its own clusters for scoring and the cost analysis of arriving at the K value. The best value is supposedly close to 1 and negative values would indicate data points assigned to wrong clusters. The K is chosen based on the high silhouette coefficient value obtained after iterating through various K values. The silhouette coefficient is usually measured based on the Euclidean distance. [23]

Given that the data provided by the authors have a non-gaussian and discrete distribution, they applied a hamming distance instead of the Euclidean distance. Post the silhouette score and cost analysis on various K values they found that K=3 would be an optimal number to reach their objective. For the visualization of clusters, they applied MCA (Multiple Correspondence Analysis) on the data in order to project it on a 3D space.

Figure 7: Silhouette plots and clusters formed on different iterations and values of K. The clusters are visualised post MCA (Multiple Correspondence Analysis) and were projected on a 3-Dimensional space. K=3 Seems to be the reasonable choice given the cost and silhouette scores.

However, we argue that previous literature suffers from certain weaknesses in identifying the asymptomatic cases that go unidentified and unnoticed described as community transmission by epidemiologists. [23]

Over time, extensive literature was published on the subject, a recent study conducted by researchers in the Department of Biostatistics at the University of Michigan developed a Spatiotemporal Epidemiological

Prediction Model to Informs County-level COVID-19 Risk in the USA [30]. They proposed a new forecast paradigm by incorporating the extended Susceptible Antibody-Infected-Removed (eSAIR) model and a cellular automata (CA) [Von Neumann et al., 1966] [6]. Being an important extension of the extended SIR (eSIR) model proposed in [Wang et al., 2020] [25], the eSAIR model enables them to capture the temporal evolution of the disease, in which a time-varying transmission rate modifier is used to account for state-specific control measures. [30]

the university of Michigan's biostatistics researchers based their model on a toolbox they developed earlier this year [25] that would provide a data analytic to people who may have better domain-specific knowledge and experience as well as high-quality data to carry out independent predictions. their informatics toolbox is built upon a state-space model shown in Figure 8. with an extended Markov SIR model [18], which has the following key features:

1. (i) the model is specified with the temporally varying prevalence of susceptible, infected and removed (recovered and death) compartments, not directly on time series of respective counts;
2. (ii) estimation and inference are carried out and implemented by the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm;
3. (iii) it outputs various sample draws from the posteriors of the model parameters (e.g. transmission and removal rates) and the underlying prevalence of susceptible, infected, and removed compartments, as well as their credible intervals. The latter is of extreme importance to quantify prediction uncertainty.[30]

Figure 8: Conceptual framework of the proposed epidemiological state-space SIR model.

In addition, this model data toolbox provides predicted turning points, including:

1. (i) the date when daily increased number of infections begins to decrease or the time at which the

second-order derivative of the prevalence of infected compartment is zero (i.e. the turning point of infection acceleration to deceleration);

2. (ii) the date when daily number of removed cases is larger than that of infected cases, or the time at which the first derivative of the prevalence of infected compartment is zero (i.e. the turning point of zero infection speed).

As a byproduct, the method provides a predicted time when the COVID-19 epidemic will ends.[18]

The basic epidemiological model with both constant transmission and removal rates in SIR model figure 8. did not reflect the reality in China earlier this year, where all levels of quarantines have been enforced. Many forms of human interventions that are altering the transmission rate over time include

1. (i) individual-level protective measures such as wearing masks and safety glasses, using hygiene, and taking in-home isolation
2. (ii) community-level quarantines such as hospitalization for infected cases, city blockade, traffic control and restricted social activities, and so on.

In addition, the virus itself may mutate to evolve, so to increase the potential rate of false-negative in the disease diagnosis. As a result, some individual virus carriers are not contained. Thus, the transmission rate indeed varies over time, which should be accounted for in the modeling. their extension to the above basic epidemiological model is to allow a time-varying probability that a susceptible person meets an infected person or vice versa.

Figure 9: An extended SIR model with time-varying transmission rates.

the chance of disease transmission when an at-risk person meets an infected person is modified as:

$$\beta\{1 - q^S(t)\}\theta_t^S\{1 - q^I(t)\}\theta_t^I := \beta\pi(t)\theta_t^S\theta_t^I,$$

with no quarantine in place, we have $\pi(t) = 1$ at all time. This resulted in a new SIR model with a time-varying transmission rate modifier represented in this equation :

$$\frac{d\theta_t^S}{dt} = -\beta\pi(t)\theta_t^S\theta_t^I, \quad \frac{d\theta_t^I}{dt} = \beta\pi(t)\theta_t^S\theta_t^I - \gamma\theta_t^I, \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d\theta_t^R}{dt} = \gamma\theta_t^I.$$

the above-extended SIR model developed by researchers assumes primarily that both population-level chance of being a susceptible and population-level chance of being infected remain the same, but the chance of a susceptible person meeting with an infected person is reduced by $\pi(t)$. The transmission

rate modifier $\pi(t)$ needs to be specified according to actual quarantine protocols in a given region. A possible choice of $\pi(t)$ may be a step function that reflects government-initiated macro isolation measures in Wuhan, Hubei province:

$$\pi(t) = \begin{cases} \pi_{01}, & \text{if } t \leq \text{Jan 23, no concrete quarantine protocols;} \\ \pi_{02}, & \text{if } t \in (\text{Jan 23, Feb 4}], \text{ city blockade;} \\ \pi_{03}, & \text{if } t \in (\text{Feb 4, Feb 8}], \text{ enhanced quarantine;} \\ \pi_{04}, & \text{if } t > \text{Feb 8, opening of new hospitals.} \end{cases}$$

When they choose different values for π_0 they obtained different types of transmission rate modifiers aligned with different quarantine protocols as shown in this graphs :

Figure 10: Transmission rate modifier takes different forms of step functions under different macro quarantine measures over time.

The modifier $\pi(t)$ may be specified as a continuous function that reflects steadily increased community-level awareness and responsibility of voluntary quarantine and preventive measures, which may be regarded as a kind of micro isolation measure initiated by individuals or local self-organized inspections, as shown in Figure 11, The authors have chosen the following exponential functions:

$$\pi(t) = \exp(-\lambda_0 t) \text{ or } \pi(t) = \exp\{-(\lambda_0 t)^\nu\}, \lambda_0 > 0, \nu > 0.$$

Figure 11: Transmission rate modifier takes continuous functions under difference micro quarantine measures over time

They then conduct an epidemiological model with

quarantine compartment, an alternative way to incorporate quarantine measures into the basic epidemiological model was to add a new quarantine compartment that collects quarantined individuals who would have no chance of meeting any infected individuals in the infection system, as shown in Figure 12. This model allows to characterize time-varying proportions of susceptible cases due largely to the government-enforced stringent in-home isolation outside of Hubei province. The basic SIR model in equation above is then extended by adding a quarantine compartment with a time-varying rate of quarantine which is the chance of a susceptible person being willing to take in-home isolation at time t.

Figure 12: An extended SIR model with time-varying transmission rate.

The extended SIR takes the following 4-dimensional latent process:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\theta_t^Q}{dt} &= \phi(t)\theta_t^S, & \frac{d\theta_t^S}{dt} &= -\beta\theta_t^S\theta_t^I - \phi(t)\theta_t^S, \\ \frac{d\theta_t^I}{dt} &= \beta\theta_t^S\theta_t^I - \gamma\theta_t^I, & \frac{d\theta_t^R}{dt} &= \gamma\theta_t^I, \end{aligned}$$

they supposed that the quarantine rate $\phi(t)$ is a Dirac delta function with jumps at times when major macro quarantine measures are enforced. They specified the $\phi(t)$ function for this task as follows:

$$\phi(t) = \begin{cases} \phi_{01}, & \text{if } t = \text{Jan 23, city blockade;} \\ \phi_{02}, & \text{if } t = \text{Feb 4, enhanced quarantine;} \\ \phi_{03}, & \text{if } t = \text{Feb 8, opening of new hospitals;} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

One of the methods that have been implemented in this research was the MCMC algorithm which was used to collect draws from the posterior distributions, and further, obtain posterior estimates and credible intervals of the unknown parameters in the above models. Because of the hierarchical structure in the state-space model considered in this paper, the posterior distributions can be obtained straightforwardly

Under-reporting of infections is a common issue in the data collection of infectious diseases, especially at the beginning of this outbreak. When medical di-

Figure 13: Three examples of multi-point instantaneous quarantine rates.

agnostic tools become more accurate and reliable, as well the transparency of preventive measures gets improved for an exchange of voluntary in-home quarantine, certain adjustments in data typically occur. It is shown in Figure 13. that on Feb 12 the cumulative and daily added number of infected cases in Hubei had clear jumps with significantly large sizes. Such sizable jumps cannot happen within one day, rather they represent an accumulation of cases that have not been reported in previous dates prior to Feb 12. To fix this under-reporting issue they developed a calibration procedure.

Figure 14: Under-reporting calibration of the infected cases in Hubei. (A) The cumulative number of infected cases. (B) The daily added number of infected cases. Data calibration is performed from Jan 13 to Feb 12 as is shown by the red curves.

It is worth pointing out that the estimates of the reproduction numbers obtained from the epidemiological models with the time-varying transmission or quarantine rates appear larger than those obtained from the basic model with no quarantine because the authors' new models explicitly incorporate interventions so that the estimated R_0 is an adjusted number with the influence of interventions be removed. In contrast, the basic model with no use of the quarantine modifier implicitly integrates the effect of interventions into the transmission rate β , and consequently, the estimated R_0 is reduced due to the contribution from interventions. their study analyses suggest that reproduction numbers R_0 of COVID-19 without public health interventions would be around 4-5 within Hubei and around 3-3.5 outside Hubei with relatively big credible intervals. The size of the credible intervals may be reduced with more accessible data of COVID-19, which permit users to specify smaller variances. [25] [30]

The proposed model conducted in this experiment utilizes the strength of the SIR's dynamic system to capture the primary mechanism of the COVID-19 infectious disease, as they were able to predict future episodes of the disease spread patterns over a window of 200 days from the last date of data availability. Some turning points of interest are obtained from these forecasting curves as part of the deliverable information, including the predicted time when daily proportion of infected cases becomes smaller than the previous ones and the predicted time when daily proportion of removed cases (i.e. both recovered and dead) becomes larger than that of infected cases, as well as the time when the epidemic ends. the informatics toolbox that was developed provides quantification of uncertainty on the prediction, rather than only point prediction values, which are valuable to see the best versus the worst.

The key novel contribution is the incorporation of time-varying quarantine protocols to expand the basic epidemiological model to accommodate changing transmission rates over time in the population. The toolbox can be used by practitioners who have a better knowledge of quarantine and better quality data to perform their own analyses. The authors also suggested that practitioners can use the toolbox to evaluate different types of quarantine strategies in practice. All summary statistics obtained from the toolbox are of great importance for public health workers and government policymakers to take proper actions to stop spreading of COVID-19.[25]

using the MCMC algorithm to implement the statistical estimation and prediction because of the consideration on the prediction uncertainty. Given the considerable complexity in the COVID19 virus spread dynamics and potentially inaccurate information of quarantine measures as well as likely under-reported proportions of infected and recovered cases and deaths, it is of critical importance to quantify and report uncertainty in the forecast. Noting that the publicly reported data of recovery and death of COVID-19 are mostly collected from hospitals where access to such information is warrant. In contrast, it is very difficult, if not impossible, to collect the data of infected individuals with light symptoms who had in-home isolation and recovered, in spite of serious efforts made by the government for a door-to-door inspection to identify suspected cases. This toolbox is indeed so general that it may be applicable to analyze and evaluate the COVID19 epidemic in other countries, as well as the future outbreak of other types of infectious diseases. [25] As noted in their paper, the proposed method does need prior data of similar infectious diseases to set up initial conditions of the infection dynamics. From this perspective, what we learned from this COVID-19 epidemic in this paper is extremely valuable to form initial conditions in the analysis of any future outbreak of similar infectious disease although a number of questions remain to be addressed.

Figure 15: Prediction plots o for Hubei with an exponential transmission rate modifier.

Same researchers from the Department of Biostatistics at the University of Michigan [25] conducted an empirical Study of Community COVID-19 Spread in the US by developing a Nationwide Risk Map this past June, since the first coronavirus case reported in Washington state in February 2020, the number of confirmed COVID-19 infections has escalated quickly from coast to coast in the US. New York was the leading state with the largest number of reported COVID-19 infections. As shown in Figure (A), up to May 2, 2020, the numbers of infected cases for New York, New Jersey, Massachusetts, Illinois, California, Pennsylvania, and Michigan follow similar patterns of the pandemic in different geographic areas. Figure (B) shows the reported cumulative number of deaths caused by COVID-19. New York is the most severely hit state with the largest reported number of deaths (a 26, 000) as of the time stamp this paper was published, while Michigan processes the highest rate of case fatality (9.5%). [25]

Figure 16: Increasing trends of COVID-19 in heavily hit states of the US up to May 2, 2020. (A) The cumulative number of reported infections since the number of infections reached 100 per state; (B) the cumulative number of deaths since the number of deaths reached 10 per state.

The daily time series of county-level confirmed infections, deaths, and recovered cases are obtained from two data sources: Harvard Dataverse [19] and 1point3acres [1]. The latter two series are combined to form a daily time series of removed cases. they tried to fit the eSAIR model separately for all continental states and Washington D.C. The results of seven severely af-

ected states are shown in the table below, including both the parameter estimates and their credible intervals for β , γ and R_0 . The Gelman-Rubin (G-R) statistic proposed by Gelman et al. [11] (with the 95 % confidence upper bound) is used to monitor MCMC convergence, in addition to other convergence diagnostics. In Table below, all the G-R statistics for MCMC draws of R_0 in the seven states equal 1, presenting clearly a piece of evidence for MCMC convergence based on four MCMC chains. Of 48 continental US states, 39 states passed the MCMC diagnostic check . [25]

State	β	γ	R_0	G-R for R_0
California	0.065 (0.043, 0.086)	0.015 (0.010, 0.022)	4.25 (2.91, 5.99)	1.001 (1.003)
Illinois	0.067 (0.054, 0.081)	0.009 (0.007, 0.012)	7.42 (5.46, 9.91)	1.001 (1.003)
Massachusetts	0.065 (0.054, 0.077)	0.011 (0.008, 0.014)	6.21 (4.76, 8.04)	1.002 (1.005)
Michigan	0.058 (0.037, 0.081)	0.020 (0.013, 0.029)	2.88 (1.96, 4.09)	1.000 (1.000)
New Jersey	0.054 (0.040, 0.067)	0.008 (0.006, 0.011)	6.66 (4.75, 8.99)	1.000 (1.000)
New York	0.061 (0.048, 0.075)	0.016 (0.011, 0.021)	3.89 (2.92, 5.15)	1.000 (1.001)
Pennsylvania	0.057 (0.038, 0.075)	0.010 (0.007, 0.014)	5.61 (3.79, 7.86)	1.000 (1.001)

Figure 17: The estimated transmission rate β , the removal rate γ , and the basic reproduction number R_0 for seven severely hit states in the US using the eSAIR model. Posterior mean and 95 % credible intervals obtained from 200,000 MCMC draws are shown for the three estimated parameters. The Gelman-Rubin (G-R) statistic for the estimation of R_0 is also shown, with the 95 % confidence upper bound in parentheses.

Figure 18: Nationwide map of 7-day ahead projected risk of COVID-19 over 3,109 counties in the continental US from May 2, 2020. Risk is classified into 5 categories.

In this article [30] , the authors propose a spatiotemporal epidemiological forecast CA-eSAIR model that provides timely predictions of community-level COVID-19 infection risk for the 3,109 continental US counties. The proposed CA-eSAIR model can make both short-term local risk predictions in one-day or one-week ahead and relatively long-term predictions like a one-month ahead. In addition, the projected county-level risk scores over a time window can be used to calculate risk for a planned trip in the US. Such a high-resolution projected risk map can particularly be useful for local governments and residents to learn the future spread patterns of the pandemic and their associated personal risks. In this empirical study, authors

have demonstrated that utilizing local information can greatly improve the prediction accuracy over the classical temporal model with no use of such information.

In addition to the new spatiotemporal prediction model, another major contribution of this paper is to incorporate the public survey results of self-immunization as an antibody compartment in the modeling of the infection dynamic system. This new antibody compartment can greatly help circumvent the under-reporting issue for data collected in a public database. The current health surveillance system in the US is incapable of capturing asymptomatic individuals with light symptoms nor being able to provide sufficient resources for the coronavirus RT-PCR diagnostic test. Recently released surveys of herd immunity in NY, CA and MA have shed light to correct the under-reporting. In the future, when more extensive surveys of similar types are to be conducted in the US, more accurate and more frequent updates of the self-immunization rate can be incorporated in the proposed eSAIR model, even possibly at the county level. The resulting CA-eSAIR would make better community-level risk prediction. [30]

In this paper, due to various limitations, several functions used in the CA-eSAIR model are not fully objective, which need to be improved in future research. The transmission rate modifier $\pi(t)$ is included to take time-varying public health interventions into account like social distancing. The state-level effectiveness of social distancing is obtained from the published values by the Transportation Institute at the University of Maryland (UMD) [27] derived from cell phone mobile data. the proposed CA-eSAIR model allows the county-level value of social distancing, but without access to high-resolution data from the UMD webpage, they used a state-level value. This may be improved in the future with better data available. Although studies have been conducted by many authors, this problem is still insufficiently explored. Since this quantity is related to many variables, it is difficult to determine it with full objectivity. Relevant to disease contagion, two major factors have been used to form this coefficient. One is an inter-county mobility index derived from mobile cell phone data; the other is a measure of inter-county travel distance. [30]

The study also introduced a tuning parameter in this metric of connectivity to optimize the contribution of travel distance by minimizing the one-day ahead prediction error. With more personal tracking data that will be available in the future, the quantification of inter-county connectivity can eventually be improved. We should note that one must exercise caution when using the proposed CA-eSAIR model for risk prediction. this previous study was limited to assuming that a person who recovers from the COVID-19 infection is immune to the coronavirus and no longer contagious. This assumption is likely to be true but has not been justified yet. Second, although the under-reporting of confirmed infections is addressed by the compartment of antibody, the under-reporting of deaths from

Figure 19: (A) The 7-day ahead county-level WAPE of infection rate for 3,109 counties in the continental US from May 2, 2020. 7th day county-level WAPE (corresponding to predictions made for May 9, 2020) is classified into 4 categories. The bins are defined by the 25th, 50th and 75th percentiles of nationwide county-specific 7th day county-level WAPE values. (B) Scatterplot of county-level weighted prediction errors (WPEs) against \log_{10} county population sizes. Three counties (namely, Los Angeles (CA), Cook (IL) and New York (NY)) are not included in order to amplify the distribution of the points.

Figure 20: Density plots comparing one-week ahead \log_{10} county-level WAPEq for 3,109 counties in the continental US from May 3, 2020 to May 9, 2020. Vertical lines for individual density curves represent the respective median values. The density curves shift to the right from May 3 to May 9, indicating an increase in county-level WAPE resulted from the increasing prediction uncertainty over time.

Figure 21: A hypothetical trip begins on May 2, 2020, with stops in Ann Arbor, Detroit, Chicago during May 3-5. Day 1: Washtenaw county (projected risk = 0.0033); Day 2: Wayne county (projected risk = 0.0127); Day 3: Cook county (projected risk = 0.0208).

the COVID-19 remains. This gives rise to a potential bias affecting the prediction accuracy. Not only is this a public health surveillance issue but a fundamental research topic in epidemiology. In reality, it is often difficult to determine a defining cause to a death with high certainty. This problem becomes even more complicated in the case of a death from the coronavirus because the medical diagnosis of "COVID-19 disease" is not clinically well defined yet.[30]

It is noteworthy that the predicted risks at some state borders like Idaho and Nebraska in Figure 21. exhibit non-smooth changes. This may be an outcome of the initial values generated from state-level eSAIR analyses in which they assume both control measures and testing policies and strategies to be state-specific, as well as the percentile-based categorization for the need of color coding in the plot. Such within-state homogeneity is also used in the prediction, resulting in more homogeneous intrastate projected risks than the inter-state projected risks. Consequently, some counties at state borders appear to have noticeable discrepancies in their projected risks. Resolving these differences at state borders may not be that simple and is beyond the capacity of their current methodology. It would be an interesting if a future work develops a method to discern the true inter-state differences from artifacts in the risk prediction for counties at state borders, where a certain objective criterion is a key to gauge adequate smoothness.

Further directions of the risk mapping method include extending the proposed CA-eSAIR model to predict the risk of the COVID-19 in other areas across the world, or to predict the risk at locations of household, factory, and business sites. The latter provides finer-

scale information of COVID19 risk critical for business reopening and allocation of resources for viral RT-PCR diagnostic tests. This in-depth analysis needs more local data of extensive viral diagnostic and antibody tests available across the country and individual health and behavior data from better surveillance systems such as mobile device apps for the tracking of personal movements. The CA-eSAIR model[30] provides a useful prediction paradigm to develop data-driven strategies for precision public health intervention and strategies for COVID-19 containment but as the authors note earlier, more work needs to be done so we can be better prepared for future pandemics.[30]

Epidemics have always existed in the world. However, their first model SIR was not published until 1902 [18]. This model and its variants are based on Markov models, where the population is divided into several classes as Susceptible, Infected or confirmed, and Recovered. In a recent scientific paper conducted by "Tecnológico Nacional de México" and "Universidad Politécnica del Estado de Morelos" titled "The Hybrid Forecasting Method SVR-ESAR for Covid-19" that focused on forecasting the confirmed class by using time series. The study was conducted using a hybrid method that uses Support Vector Regression (SVR), Exponential Smoothing (ES), and ARIMA. [10]

These techniques are widespread in several platforms. Seminal contributions have been made by The paper presents a forecasting method named SVR-ESAR (Support Vector Regression with Exponential Smoothing and ARIMA), which was applied for the estimation of confirmed (infected) cases of Covid-19 in four scenarios (the Whole World, China, the US, and Mexico). This method is straightforward and uses SVR with an iterative adjustment phase. In the adjustment phase, the authors applied three algorithms to the SVR residuals: ES, SVR, and ARIMA and found that SVR-ESAR with an ARIMA adjustment obtained the best or equivalent results for all these scenarios. They then applied this method for data of Mexico with modest quality results. However, the results of SVR-ESAR were compared with those published in the literature for the US and China and found the proposed method achieved the best predictions. [10]

The SVR-ESAR Architecture GA-SVR has two phases and is shown in The Figure below:

1. Phase 1: A Genetic Algorithm adjusts the parameters of an SVR machine and its kernels (linear, RBF, sigmoid) using Grid Search and iteratively improves the $F^*(t)$ forecast of SVR [24]. The improved forecast $F^{*1}(t)$ in this phase has a MAPE error dependent on the residuals during the training phase.
2. Phase 2: Three alternative techniques obtain a correction of the $F^{*1}(t)$ forecast previously obtained by GA-SVR in phase 1: SVR, Holt Exponential Smoothing (ES), and ARIMA [14]. These techniques are applied to the residuals between $F^{*1}(t)$

) and the actual values in the training stage, and obtaining a better forecasting F_{2svr} , F_{2ES} , and F_{2AR} with the application in the second phase of these three techniques SVR, ES, and ARIMA respectively. [10]

The presented forecasting method was applied to people infected with Coronavid 19. The period for this time series is from 22/January until 25/April/ 2020 [5].

The experimental results show four different scenarios:

1. The Whole World: The forecasting results obtained for infected people [5] compared with the results obtained for their proposed forecasting method using the infected cases.
2. China: This country was the origin of the pandemic. There are published results for this case [4], which the authors used in this section for validating the proposed method.
3. United States (US): This country has the highest number of incidences in the American continent; also, it is significant because it has a lot of communication with the rest of the world.
4. Mexico implemented some particular policies and has a lot of relationships with many countries, particularly with the US, and Canada. [10]

Table in Figure 22. presents the results for the Whole World and China, obtained with the application of the proposed method for confirmed forecasting case. In this table, the study shows the results of SVR-ESAR using the adjustment techniques SVR, ES, and ARIMA. they noticed that all these techniques have a small value of MAPE error. the results obtained for this case in [20] and [9]. They also observed that SVR-ARIMA achieved the best results for these cases. Furthermore, Figure 2 shows the results obtained by SVR-ESAR for these scenarios. [10]

in Figure 23 the forecasting confirmed results for the US and Mexico obtained with SVR-ESAR. the results of the proposed method using the adjustment obtained by SVR, ES, and ARIMA is in Figure 24). In the case of the US, the ARIMA adjustment technique achieves the

Scenario 1: Infected in the Whole Word.				
Forecasting method	Exponential Smoothing, [15]		SVR-ESAR	
	Adjusted Technique:		Adjusted Technique	
	Multiplicative Trend model	SVR	ES	Arima
MAPE error (%)	6.9	2.46	0.77	0.56
Scenario 2: Infected in China				
Forecasting method	Neural Networks [4]		SVR-ESAR	
	Adjusted Technique		Adjusted Technique	
	Unknown	SVR	ES	Arima
MAPE error (%)	4.79	1.90	3.53	1.41

Figure 22: SVR-ESAR Architecture.

Scenario 3 and 4: Infected in United States and Mexico			
Forecasting Method	SVR-ESAR		
	Adjusted Technique		
	SVR	ES	Arima
MAPE US (%)	5.09	5.39	0.90
MAPE Mexico (%)	12.44	13.25	12.57

Figure 23: Forecasting for the infected in the Whole World and China using the SVR-ESAR method with three adjustment techniques (SVR, Exponential Smoothing, and ARIMA).

best result. This table also shows the results obtained by SVR-ESAR for Mexico but this time the proposed method achieves a modest forecasting result with all three adjustment techniques.

Figure 24: The forecasting of infected cases for the US and Mexico.

5 Summary

Human civilization has progressed from the Stone Age to Agricultural and then to the Industrial Age. We are now in the present ‘information’ age. Humans are basically makers of tools. From the stone age, we have strengthened our capability to survive by enhancing the quality of our tools, mostly weaponry. Once we started to convey ideas in abstract forms through drawings and language and as we improved methods of storing information, the capability to make sophisticated tools increased near exponentially by the industrial age. Humans no longer remain stuck in their regular and mundane survival activities like hunting for food. They started developing methods and means to understand the nature surrounding them. The very first step in this direction was to understand the material world. [2]

Molecular Biology has lately become heir to a huge legacy of standardized data in the form of polynucleotide and polypeptide sequences. With the explosion of recorded information, biochemists for the first time found it necessary to familiarize themselves with databases and the algorithms needed to extract the correlations of records, and in turn have put these to good use in the exploration of phylogenetic relationships, and in the applied tasks of hunting genes and their often valuable products. The formalization of this research challenge in the Human Genome Project has generated a new impetus in datasets to be analyzed and the funds to support that research[21]

The current volume is an effort to bridge just that range of exploration, from nucleotide to abstract concept, in contemporary AI research. That bridge must also join computer scientists with laboratory biochemists afterword outlines some of the hazards of taking biologists’ last word as the settled truth, and therefore the imperative of mutual understanding about how imputed knowledge will be used. A variety of target problems, and perhaps a hand-crafted representation for each, is embraced in the roster. There is an obvious

detriment to premature standardization;

One of the major challenges for computer scientists who wish to work in the domain of molecular biology is becoming conversant with the daunting intricacies of existing biological knowledge and its extensive technical vocabulary. Questions about the origin, function, and structure of living systems have been pursued by nearly all cultures throughout history, and the work of the last two generations has been particularly fruitful. The knowledge of living systems resulting from this research is far too detailed and complex for any human to comprehend. [3] This paper presents a comparative analysis of CA and soft computing models to predict the COVID-19 outbreak. The results of CA models reported a high generalization ability for long-term prediction. With respect to the results reported in the papers we cover and due to the highly complex nature of the COVID-19 outbreak and differences from nation-to-nation, this study suggests that CA is an effective tool to model the time series of the outbreak.

We should note that this paper provides an initial benchmarking to demonstrate the potential of machine learning for future research. For the advancement of higher performance models for long-term prediction, future research should be devoted to comparative studies on various CA models for individual countries. Due to the fundamental differences between the outbreak in various countries, the advancement of global models with generalization ability would not be feasible. As observed and reported in many studies, it is unlikely that an individual outbreak will be replicated elsewhere. A more systematic and theoretical analysis is required to learn from the coronavirus pandemic so we can be better prepared for the Next unpreventable Disease Outbreak. [3]

The upsurge of interest in machine learning owes much to an increasing understanding of the scientific potential of Artificial Intelligence. This article explains in a lucid and straightforward way how these methods are used by scientists and what we can accomplish with them. Recognizing that not all experimental scientists are computer experts. Computer scientists may use this article to gain a clearer picture of how experimental scientists use Artificial Intelligence tools. Chemists, biochemists, physicists, and others in the experimental sciences who have data to analyze or simulations to run will find tools within these pages that may speed up their work or make it more effective. For both groups, the aim of this article is to encourage a broader application of these methods. [13] It is still early in the era of applying machine learning to vaccine design. A machine learning model is only as good as its training data, and current immunology models are trained on much smaller datasets compared to models for voice recognition or facial recognition, areas in which artificial intelligence has excelled. So hopefully in the near future, we can use machine learning to speed the process of vaccine creations.[7]

6 Author Biography

Figure 25: Khaoula Hidawi

I obtained my Bachelor of Science and Associate of Science in Applied Mathematics And Computer Sciences from The Faculty Of Science Semlalia , University of Cadi Ayaad Marrakesh in 2019 and a Baccalauréat in Mathematical Sciences option B from the Technical high school Mohammed VI back in 2015. I'm currently a master degree student in Cyber security and Cyber-crimes at The National School of Applied Sciences in Tangier .

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